

In terms of infection rate, *Oryza nivara* and *O. nivara*-derived varieties IR42 and IR54 were resistant to M3 and S2, susceptible to M2, and moderately

susceptible to SC. TN1 was resistant to M3, susceptible to M2 and SC, and moderately susceptible to S2. The four isolates do not fall under either RGSV 1

or RGSV 2 categories, which were previously reported in the Philippines. Results indicate that many RGSV strains exist in the Philippines. □

Effect of changing the agricultural environment on ufra occurrence in the Mekong Delta

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Ufra is caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*. Yield losses of 50-100% have been reported in deepwater rice (DWR) fields in the Mekong Delta where ufra occurs during high water levels.

Supplemental irrigation facilities have caused low-yielding DWR to be abandoned in favor of one or two high-yielding rice crops before and after flooding (Table 1). In Dong Thap Province, for example, more than 100,000 ha of DWR was grown in 1976; ufra affected 60,000 ha. Modern rice cultivars were grown on 60,000 ha of

Table 1. Areas damaged by *D. angustus* and land use in 5 provinces of the Mekong Delta in Vietnam, 1976-90.

Year	Damaged area (ha)	Area planted (ha)	
		Deepwater rice	Irrigated rice
<i>Cuu Long</i>			
1985	2,798	141,970	40,824
1988	1,133	105,845	75,366
1990	906	95,245	80,870
<i>Dong Thap</i>			
1976	60,000	110,839	0
1981	10,000	80,000	0
1990	20	15,000	60,000
<i>Hau Giang</i>			
1982	17,900	320,517	27,378
1985	3,700	296,242	56,100
1988	1,284	252,068	71,287
1990	804	210,830	104,323
<i>An Giang</i>			
1976	2,500	152,692	31,509
1980	210	145,875	79,066
1985	5	83,964	97,632
1990	0	37,347	141,210
<i>Beu Tre</i>			
1976	10,000	83,975	0
1980	71	54,834	3,500
1985	62	63,133	19,160
1990	0	53,420	23,536

irrigated land in 1990 and DWR on 15,000 ha. Ufra disease drastically declined with this change: in 1990 only 20 ha were damaged. The same trend was observed in other provinces, such as An Giang.

Large areas are still planted to DWR in Hau Giang Province. The 800 ha damaged in 1990 was mainly in Phung Hiep and Ke Sack where *D. angustus*-affected areas are decreasing as DWR areas decline (Table 2). The trend was similar in Cuu Long and Beu Tre provinces.

Modern irrigated rice varieties are susceptible to ufra and a few infested plants are often observed. *D. angustus*, however, needs at least 75% atmospheric humidity to infest the foliage. Low rainfall limits ufra occurrence and crop damage is insignificant.

Table 2. Areas infested with *D. angustus* and land use in 2 districts of Hau Giang Province, Vietnam, 1982-90.

Year	Infested area (ha)	Area planted (ha)	
		Deepwater rice	Irrigated rice
<i>Phung Hiep</i>			
1982	2,560	27,006	1,034
1985	1,199	23,468	2,900
1988	620	22,550	4,355
1990	300	19,640	7,260
<i>Ke Sack</i>			
1983	1,700	10,600	2,580
1985	1,300	9,070	8,000
1987	250	7,793	10,600
1990	185	7,913	9,587

Dikes and levees protect the wet season crop against early flooding, and thus prevent or delay plant infestation by *D. angustus*. □

Integrated pest management—insects

Stalk-eyed fly (SEF) damage to lowland irrigated rices in Nigeria

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SEF *Diopsis longicornis* Macquart is a dipteran stem borer that attacks rice in Africa. SEF larvae feed on tillers internally and cause deadhearts. Infested tillers become sterile.

We monitored SEF damage on two commonly cultivated lowland irrigated rices (ITA2 12 and Suakoko 8) under natural field conditions at IITA during 1990 wet season.

Seedlings (21 d old) were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in two fields (each 650 m²), one seedling/hill.

We assessed SEF damage on rice by

counting total tillers and infested tillers in 100 randomly selected hills, expressed as percent damage weekly from 14 to 56 d after transplanting (DT).

The most SEF damage on both varieties was observed at 14 DT. This suggests that SEF oviposits on rice seedlings in nursery beds. Damage declined after 14 d, but more abruptly on Suakoko 8, possibly because ITA212 is shorter and more high tillering (see figure).

SEF damage to lowland irrigated rice in IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria, 1990 ws.